

NDAC/LO/069

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15th NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

WP8000: Double Stars (Söderhjelm)

Simulations of wide (2-36") double stars were continued and have resulted in relatively firm estimates of the observability and resulting errors as function of separation, magnitude difference, and observing strategy (C). An improved weighting scheme was developed, based on observed quantities rather than on *a priori* assumptions (C). The degradation in case the slit width is wider than nominal was also investigated by simulation (C). Work is now in progress concerning close pairs and pairs without a good *a priori* knowledge of ρ and θ .

Miscellaneous (Lindegren)

The 9th run of ESTEC photon counts simulations was analysed with the Lund IDT preprocessing software (C). The results, with and without binning, have been sent on magnetic tape to Vaghi (ESTEC).

Working papers

- C Söderhjelm 1985 Dec 10: HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, I.
(NDAC/LO/066)
- C Söderhjelm 1986 Febr 4: HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, Ib.
(NDAC/LO/067)
- C Lindegren 1986 Febr 19: Preprocessing of ESTEC photon counts
(NDAC/LO/068) simulations, Run No 9